

Methods of Detecting Lone-Wolf Terrorism

By Edwin Amuga

Abstract

Lone-wolf terrorism widely has been ignored by researchers and anti-terror authorities in spite of the rising number of attacks attributed to it. Lone-wolf terrorism has brought in new challenges to counterterrorism and law enforcement different from the much discussed problems of international terrorism due to its nature.

This thesis approaches policies that can help detect and deter lone-wolf terrorism and includes the suitability of those used in confronting international group terrorism. The existing policy framework on curbing and deterring international group terrorism may be very useful in confronting lone wolf-terror. This though has to be approached and examined carefully for effective use since this needs close look at unique characteristics of lone-terrorism to ensure a match between deterrence policies. This thesis comparatively examines lone wolf terrorism case studies in Europe and the United States: 2009 Fort Hood Indiscriminate shooting by Major Nidal Hasan, Norway's Anders Breivick and Boston Marathon Bombing. This thesis takes a look into the effective policies and ineffective ones in the face of these unique circumstances in the need to adapt and prevent lone-terrorism threats.

Keywords: Case study, lone-wolf terrorism, radicalization, law enforcement agency, counter-terrorism.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

The Norwegian Breivik rampage in 2011 is still a much referred to example in the international discourse. Lone-wolf terrorist attacks have been discussed and talked about by world leaders calling for action to stop them. Most global terrorism policies are focused on preventing and deterring international group terrorism and largely ignore lone-wolf terrorism. The US Congressional Research Service, for example, lists 1,649 terrorism reports and lone-wolf terrorism is addressed in only ten and of these all concentrate on lone-wolf terrorism as provided by FISA. This thesis delves into major question and key to stopping lone wolf terrorism attacks by looking at the methods of detecting them.

Problem Statement

Lone-wolf terrorism has been on the rise in the last decade fuelled by a combination of social media and internet ubiquity that in turn fuel radicalization within and without state boundaries thereby posing new challenges to counterterrorism and law enforcement efforts. Recent years studies on terrorism have been focusing on international group terrorism and as a result many counterterrorism and law enforcement policies have been formulated to detect and prevent radicalization and participation in organized terrorist activities. Potential and developing criminal upstream could be intervened by identifying the common ideological beliefs, psychological patterns, traits, education and training data on lone wolf radicalization patterns and prevent attacks before they are carried out. Worship places, neighborhoods, campuses and other social

centers could be well secured and lone wolf terrorism could be well prevented if this research question is well answered. This thesis takes a look into lone-wolf terrorism characteristics of foiled and successful acts. It also intends to answer questions on identification mechanism for lone-wolf terrorism and the required policy changes, adoptions and improvements so that lone-wolf terrorism threats can be identified and addressed.

General Research Question

New counterterrorism and law enforcement challenges have been registered due to the nature lone-wolf terrorists that are different from the much focused-on international group form of terror. This form of terror is an old phenomenon but the focus has predominantly been on 'large scale' counterterrorism efforts worldwide. High scale vigilance has to be exercised to detect and prevent terrorist threats that seek to penetrate all avenues of national boundaries that are through land, sea and air. Relationships have to be built between first responders in the community and law enforcers in an effort to confront self-radicalization and violence since lone-wolf terrorist dwell quietly in the midst of a populace inspired by radical violent ideologies. This thesis seeks to answer the question; can ideological beliefs, attributes, psychological factors, education and training unearth radicalization patterns that will provide law enforcement agencies with the criteria to identify up-coming lone wolf terrorists?

Background and Significance

Before opening fire at Fort Hood killing 13 and infuring 42, Nidal Hasan shouted ‘Allah Akbar’, Arabic for God is great. This thesis examines Nadal’s background to determine the thresholds an attack has to meet to be considered lone wolf terrorism. The specifics of the terror acts are reviewed followed by a review of findings of official documents concluded with key point summery.

There is an ongoing debate on whether Hasan’s actions were terrorism or not. Simon (2013) considered his acts as workplace violence rather than a terrorist act. A number of commentators have fronted arguments on why this action was not declared an act of terror even by the US Government. Gill, Horgan and Deckert, (2014) hypothesize that this is because Hasan was a US army officer and the US government and counterterrorist agencies did want to discredit the army and the government. Despite these steps, the fort hood shooting incident has been used in counterterrorism classes and lessons even reported to the senate of the United States. Refereeing to definitions in chapter one in this thesis, Hassan’s action were clearly acts of terrorism and more specifically lone-wolf. Horgan (2015) classifies indiscriminate shootings as an act of terrorism. This action is classified under lone wolf terrorism because of the motivation factors and the massacre he perpetrated. A great number of scholars, victims of the shootings and the public considered Hasan’s terroristic acts as the religious type; perpetrating religious violence.

Major Hasan was an American citizen by birth born in Arlington Virginia in 1970 of Palestinian parents and raised a Muslim in an Islamic household. He graduated from a

Virginian High school and joined the US army and attained a degree in biochemistry in 1995 and later earned medical degree and as a result becoming an Army psychiatrist. Hassan therefore began life as many Americans.

Hassan's actions followed the for radicalization stages. US war on terror, life situation and parents' death marked the start of this pre-radicalization stage. The latter propelled him to becoming more religious leading to self-identification with Islamic extremist ideologies. He began the indoctrination stage when he started attending the mosque. His jihadist phase is not clear but he was on record talking against the War on Terror and inter-Muslim fights.

As part of an ongoing investigation on the mosque leader which Hasan attended, a message to the leader from Hassan was acquired by the FBI thereby attracting its attention which prompted further investigations that resulted in his name being mentioned in terrorism task forces both in Washington and San Diego. An assessment was conducted by Washington office on his department of defense records and came up with the conclusion that he had no links to terrorist activities or groups. Interviewing him was ruled out since this would jeopardize efforts of investigating the mosque leader and would therefore be self-defeating.

He was transferred to Fort Hood in July 2009 and informed that he would be deployed to Afghanistan in a few months' time. He committed the act on 5th of November 2009 ahead of his Afghanistan deployment and the FBI took no step until after he committed the acts.

The FBI started improving its lone wolf terrorism detection abilities to deter threats such as the one perpetrated by Hassan. The steps taken to do this focused on information sharing between the Department of Defense and the FBI primarily, FBI involvement in National security cases, improvement of information technology and training. These actions were prompted by the shortcomings in the detection and prevention of lone wolf threats.

Hasan's case is a clear wolf terrorism based on common descriptions, definitions and typologies. It proves that lone wolf terrorism is complex and difficult in nature that law enforcement agencies and counterterrorism formations are faced with. Experts in the FBI watched Hassan for over a year and failed to detect and stop his terrorist intentions as it was even clear that Hassan attempted to finance terrorist activities by donating money to the mentioned mosque leader and claimed to do so legally. This information was in the possession of the FBI in form of emails between two yet no terrorism link was found which would otherwise have been found if interviews with Hassan or anyone associated with him and also failed to contact any law enforcement agency with regard to Hasan's lone wolf terrorist suspicion as subsequently failing to detect and stop lone wolf attack at the Ford Hood.

A number of the policies need reexamination to help identify and stop lone wolf terrorists. These policies have to involve the internet, law enforcement lead agency function, local community contacting and community outreach programs.

In another similar scenario, two explosions took place Boston Marathon finish line on 15th of April 2013 and investigations were launched. A pressure cooker bomb was used and claimed three lives and injured 200 more. Tsarnaey brothers were identified by the authorities as Tamerlan and Dzhokhar as being behind the explosions. Tamerlan succumbed to bullets as a result of a shootout with the police while Dzhokhar was captured after a nationwide manhunt. A police officer lost his life in the manhunt bringing the death toll connected with the bombings to four with 200 casualties. The United States was shaken by the terror attack much as the 9/11. This case study presented unique aspects and lens of lone-wolf terror acts.

The Boston Marathon occurrences were lone-wolf terroristic for certain reasons first, the perpetrators with their acts are in the definitions in the first chapter in this thesis. Due to the fact that they were not linked to any terrorist organization and acted together in perpetrating the act. The brothers are also described in one of the typologies; the religious type mentioned in the first chapter of this thesis since they yelled Islamic utterances before committing terrorism. The elder of the brothers was disgruntled with the USA and prompted him to indulge in the cats while the younger one Dzhokhar was a well-linked social person who had no history of violence. He attended Cambridge Ridge High school and Latin school in Cambridge, Massachusetts and after graduating proceeded to the University of Masachusets in 2011 at Dartmouth. He became a naturalized citizen of the United States on September 11th 2012.

He was therefore a normal college student by all counts who was an athlete and a good student in high school. His acts of terrorism during the Boston marathon point to the fact that this form of terror can be perpetrated by anybody from anywhere.

A number of reports point out to the fact that Tamerlan was willing to get involved in radicalization on jihadist ideologies against the west. Russian Federal Security Service sent a letter to the FBI expressing concern on Tamerlan's radicalization and was concerned that he would join terrorist groups upon returning to Russia after reports that he had hoped to fly to Palestine to wage jihad but changed his mind because he could not speak Arabic.

The Russian agency was concerned that he was had ties with Caucasus militants where he comes from. This was done to request more information but the effort did not go through. The FBI conducted investigations and interviews with him and his parents but links to terrorism was not found. This went unnoticed even as Kathrine Russel's friends reported that he took more extremist views as time went on when they were dating. Tamerlan's travel to Russia on Jan 2012 contributed into his radicalization and ideological process. The FBI later learned that he shared jihadist videos and articles a head of his Russian visit. Termalan's YouTube channel in which he watched and posted Islamist extremist videos were discovered after the bombing. Anwar al Awlaki-The mosque leader's influence showed up at the Boston Marathon case as it was in Major Nadal Hasan's case.

An article entitled was also discovered in his computer in an online magazine inspired and created by the mosque leader. The article advocated for the use of a pressure cooker to make bombs for lone wolf attacks. Tsarnaev was also reported by have attended the leader's mosque several times as fronted by Islamist Society of Boston Cultural Centre in a public statement adding that he even engaged in verbal confrontations with preachers and suspended on several occasions. This was in form of accusing preachers of being 'non believers' and 'hypocrites' after they encouraged the celebration of American holidays in the mosque. He was therefore inspired by personal issues and radical Islam as the factors that shaped his life to terror as it has become evident that he had Islamist extremist view fascination and this the authorities failed to notice.

His brother's radicalization and ideological factors were not much focused on owing to the on-going criminal trails against him for involvement in the Boston bombings. He was however reported to having been looking up to his elder brother with admiration which is one of the factors that shaped his path to terror and this was evidenced by his dropping grades and social awkwardness that he exhibited before the bombing as reported by his friends. Police recovered a note from him during his capture stating that the bombing was a retaliatory move for the American incursion and attacks in Muslim lands. This proves that this was a case of lone wolf attack of religious typology.

The four stages of radicalization were also exhibited in this case as highlighted in the first chapter of this thesis especially in Tamerlan's radicalization path that shaped his

actions to lone wolf terrorism. His life experiences as a failed career boxer put him in the pre-radicalization phase as he developed grudge with the United States and become more religious after this giving himself identity with Islamic extremism. His indoctrination phase started in 2009 after his failures and developed appeal for extremist Islamic views. The jihadization stage followed between 2009 and 2013 owing to his Russian travel and reading of extremist articles and videos as evidenced by his outspoken nature from extremism in the mosque. His jihadization was fueled by the Muslim leader Awlaki reported to have been his inner convictions on the United States and would lead him the path to perpetrate terror.

The FBI identifies Tsarnaev brothers as bombing suspects by April 19th 2013 after reviewing its 2013 records and found out that the Russian federal security service provided it with crucial leads in Tamerlan's involvement in terrorism and assessed him but closed it after it found no link to terrorism.

He remained in the Bureau's watch list even after the assessment. During Department of justice official review on the available information on the bombings, the FBI counter terror agent who as in charge of Tamerlan's case was found not to have conducted a full assessment and contact law enforcement which would have unearthed jihadist videos and articles. The younger brother did not feature in the assessment and his involvement only came up at the action time.

The Boston Marathon Bombings point to a case of lone-wolf terrorism as they show limited public safety from lone wolf attackers. The FBI failed to protect the public

from terrorism as also witnessed in the case of Nidal Hasan since its terrorism assessments were shrewd claiming that it had changed its assessment conducting procedures despite the failures seen in the case of Nidal Hasan instead of contacting law enforcement in the case of Tamerlan which would have provided more information that would have linked him with terror for appropriate action to be taken.

Four people lost their lives and 200 more others injured due to this negligence by the FBI. This calls for United States domestic policy changes to help protect the public from threats posed by lone wolf terrorists. These policy weaknesses were also evident in the case of Nidal Hasan in policies involving internet, investigative organ's lead agency function and responsibility and community outreach programs.

In another lone-wolf case, Anders Breivick set off a car bomb on 22nd July 2009 outside governmental buildings in Oslo, Norway, killing eight people and injuring scores. He travelled by boat to Utoya Island after committing the terror act to Ruling Labor Party's summer camp for children. He was in police uniform and opened fire on workers, campers and other attendants and killed 69 people bringing the death toll attributed to his two lone wolf actions to 77 (Becker, 2014).

His actions and tactics were on their own kind as a lone wolf terrorist as he was the first to perpetrate tacks of the magnitude combining jihadist modus operandi, school shooting and right-wing extremist mix of tactics. The case has unique aspects embodied in lone wolf terrorism as it offers the international perspective of looking at lone wolf

terrorism closing arguments that lone wolf terrorism is a problem only experienced in the United States.

Referring to definition of Simon (2013) into consideration in chapter one, the Norwegian lone wolf terrorist acted alone without orders from anyone or group. He also meets the criteria to be a lone wolf terrorist typology different from the other cases in chapter 1. This form of terrorism cuts across all borders of political, religious and cultural spectrum as opposed to Islamic terrorist groups such as the Al Qaeda. It undermines the belief that only Islamist groups can perform terror acts as Breivick was pursuing anti-Islamic and anti-migration agenda in Europe. He was referred to by Spaaij and Hamm (2015) as 'copy and paste terrorist' due to the fact that he mixed terrorist tactics and ideologies in pursuing his agenda. In its report on terrorism, Europol referred to Breivick as a lone-wolf terrorist because he targeted Norway's political system.

Breivick was an English citizen born in 1979. He attended an elite high school and proceeded to join an anti free market and immigration youth group at the age of 16. He in the year 2000 stood against islamization of Europe and European multiculturalism. This thinking radicalized him before committing the act of terror.

He was reported to have developed paranoia from obsessions with history and politics. This is evidence that he passed through terrorism path that changed his view of the Norwegian society.

Breivick was an anti-Islamic and right wing extremist opposing multi-culturalization of Europe with his terroristic mind shaped by his early life events leading

to acting as a lone wolf terrorist. The anti-Islam stand transformed this thinking from the time he fell out with a Muslim friend for attacking him. He also kept himself up to date with information and reports of Norwegian women being raped by immigrant Muslims and Norwegian men. NATO war on Serbia also further radicalized him since he considered NATO anti-European in the way.

He operated on extremist communities online fringes as he was actively participating in online far-right and anti-Muslim views and was in contact with other far-right fringe individuals but never tipped on his plans online. He was unhappy with clash of ideologies and cultures globally which has been his defining feature in the last ten years before the attack. It appeared that he had been thinking about this attack plan for almost ten years but he directly began planning it a year before the attack date with time before that dedicated to fund raising and ideological formation. These twisted his perspectives and perception of the environment and propelled him to committing terror acts which in his view was a greater good for all Europeans within and without Norway.

Breivick wasn't in the right-wing extremist register in possession of the police. He landed himself in the Norwegian security services watch list in 2011 after buying large amounts of fertilizer from a Polish online store but the police assumed that they were meant for a rented farm since he was a law abiding citizen with no terrorist characteristics and remained totally tolerant in online statements. His attack on the island would have had even a higher number of victims due to the location of the island and the

delayed police response. He was tried with murder of 77 people and sentenced to over 20 years in prison.

Breivick was a lone wolf terrorist who invested huge amounts of time in planning the attacks and as a result succeeded in killing many innocent people. His case proved that lone wolf terrorists have no boundaries whatsoever but the authorities have the capability to stop such terrorist before they strike since most of them appear in investigative bodies' watch lists due to behaviors exhibited in the past in terms of change of moods and demeanor ahead of their attack. Breivick was radicalized online but did not show signs that would cause suspicions. These factors would have given the Norwegian police a reason to go ahead with investigations and stop him before innocent should were lost in hid killing spree. This case is proof that there is always something that can be done to stop lone wolf terrorists since they display peculiar signs.

Specific Research Question

Lone-wolf terror is an old problem that is reemerging and policies used to detect and prevent international group terrorism can be used to detect and prevent it. This though has to be done closely and carefully to make the policies applicable in this new terrorism strain. Terrorist attacks attributed to lone-wolf terrorism have been on the rise in America and Europe launching a major terrorist operation should not be of focus in light of lone-wolf terrorism since this is a case of a person with a single weapon carrying out wide-scale killings. This is because these operations are most likely to be large, well-

coordinated counterterrorist attacks rather than being a lone-wolf operation. This thesis therefore seeks to answer the question; what are the most viable methods that could be used to detect and identify lone-wolf terrorists and their activities before they strike?

Research Aim and Objective

The thesis identifies lone-wolf terrorist features, ignite lone-wolf terrorism policy debate, identify possible solutions and extend the short list of lone-wolf terrorism research works. This study seeks to answer unanswered questions regarding lone-wolf terrorism and help boost the understanding of the phenomenon.

Thesis Structure

The 9/11 attacks changed the way the world thought and looked at terrorism showing that terrorists can go a long way and great lengths to pursue their goals. Different countries implemented policies and laws on war against terrorism and their efforts have reduced the likelihood of future terrorist attacks in victim countries such as the United States. These efforts such as the US Patriotic Act in concert with war against terror have resulted in groups such as the al Qaeda decentralizing. Decentralization here implies that these terrorist groups are resorting more to lone wolf terrorist attacks shifting from group based attacks. This means that the most likely form of terrorism that will confront countries in the future is lone wolf terrorism; this thesis has four chapters. Chapter one provides introduction, research question, thesis relevance explanation, literature review, and a road map. The second, third and fourth chapters delves into

successful lone wolf terrorism acts, chapter two is the literature reviews and three is the theoretical framework, the first chapter focuses on research design.

Each case examines and analyses the background of the actors followed by terror act specifics, and review of findings of official documents and summery. The thesis analyses policies that may need to be adopted, changed or enacted to help detect and confront the growing lone wolf terror by counterterrorism experts and law enforcement agencies.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

Academic literature has ignored this topic since the focus has been on international group-based terror and literature and research have since the United States' 9/11 terrorist attacks been done examining international terrorism. This focus has been persistent regardless of the recent skyrocketing attacks attributed to lone-wolf terrorism (Striegher, 2013). This is evidenced by the fact that there has not occurred an international terrorist incident of the same nor even greater than 9/11 attacks but there has been persistent reoccurrence of lone-wolf terrorist attacks even greater than the Norwegian Lone-wolf terrorist attacks on Europe by Anders Behring Breivik.

1. Lone-wolf terrorism-definition

The biggest point of concern before defining this term lies on understanding why an individual is to be regarded as a lone-wolf. The term suggests that an individual is involved in the terrorist activities. Feldman (2013) describes it as using violent threats and sabotage that's non-violent to in advancement of financial, religious, political and social and other related goals or effect related objectives upon society, government, military or business and interfering with daily life by disruption on the affected entities by creating fear triggering heightened security or excessive force response. He adds that these threats can also be inform of cyber-attacks.

Becker (2014) defines it more broadly as an independent individual's political violence perpetration without affiliation to or commanding from top organized terror groups or networks and therefore use methods and tactics they direct and conceive independently. Referring to this definition, Anders Behring Breivick was a lone-wolf terrorist. He argues that lone wolf terrorist has no relationship with, connected to or supported by an outside group which according to him, is the key point in the definition of lone-wolf terrorists. By Becker's (2014) definition, the key point in lone wolf terrorism lies on the number of involved terrorists and not in the support received from outside groups. By combining the two definitions in evaluating this form of terror, this paper argues that the number of lone wolf terrorists does not determine the occurrence of lone wolf attacks but organizational lack of support for the attack. Moskalenko and McCauley (2013) portend that a lone individual conducts lone-wolf terrorism conceiving and directing his actions independent of any command structure, formal or informal.

Simon (2013) approaches lone wolf terrorism as terrorism perpetrated by independent individuals not connected to any terror network and conceives and directs their modiooperandi individually without outside command influence. The Federal Bureau of Investigation defines this terrorism type as homegrown and domestic form of terrorism that is inspired ideologically by formal terrorist formations (Spaajj & Hamm, 2015). FBI admits that this form of terrorism remains anonymous to law enforcement detection and prevention capabilities. Simon (2016) argues that this form of terrorism can effect high profile destructive attacks on lives and infrastructure and create huge chaos despite the limited resources and unnatural methodology.

This thesis therefore looks at it as terrorist activities perpetrated by individuals who conduct terror acts without higher chain of command orders and are not affiliated to any organized terror groups but may have been trained in the past or had contact with terrorist groups and draw ideologies and motivation from organized terror networks (Kaplan, Lööw & Malkki, 2014). Lone-wolf terrorism wages violence against civilian, government, military, society targets in efforts to advance their ideological motives.

In spite of lone-wolf terrorism's wide variety of descriptions and definitions, the fact that lone wolf terrorists are not affiliated to or are members of known terror groups and do not take orders from them remains unchanged (Reid Meloy & Yakeley, 2014). No definition disputes the fact that lone-wolf terrorism is becoming a major security threat. Usage of non-violent sabotage, violence threat and military, government, business, society or any target by an individual lone wolf terrorist to advance their social, religious, political or financial agenda by disrupting peaceful daily life and attracting heightened security measures and responses (Michael, 2014). All the perpetrators in all the three case studies were therefore lone-wolf terrorists.

2. Lone-Wolf Terrorism Motivational and Ideological Factors

McCauley, Moskalkenko and Van Son (2013) identify various factors motivational to lone-wolf terrorists that can be used to categorize these terrorists and their acts and three of them apply to terrorist groups. Of the five factors, the first type of this form of terrorists is secular lone wolf terrorists that commit violent attacks on ethno-nationalist, separatist and political causes. The second is the religious type that commits religious

related violence (Gruenewald, Chermak, & Freilich, 2013). The third of the types is the single-issue lone wolf terrorists unleashing attacks on specific issues such as abortions as their reasons. The idiosyncratic lone-wolf terrorists are the fourth type that commit terror on cause such as personality and psychological problems driving them to violence. The fifth is the lone-wolf type of terrorists quite unique from all the other types described by Simon (2013) and is motivated by money and as a result of this are referred to as criminal lone wolf terrorists. These highlighted typologies are therefore crucial in the understanding and identification lone-wolf terrorism.

3. Scholarly studies on lone-wolf terrorism

Three studies on western lone-wolf attacks have been conducted that focus on the characteristics of lone terrorist and can be used to identify them. A study by Simon (2013) on lone-wolf terrorism research agenda and key issues is the earliest followed by McCauley, Moskalenko and Van Son (2013) research on conflict and terrorism. He examined 3,000 terrorism cases in a four year period from 1995 to 1999 in the United States and discovered that 30 of them were lone-wolf terrorism. He contends that psychological disturbance rates are higher among lone-wolf terrorist than in international group based terrorists and this fact can therefore be used to characterize and identify lone-wolf terrorists before they unleash terror. Philips (2013) also concluded that 198 lone wolf terrorist attack cases were carried out in Europe, Canada, Australia and the United States from 1940 to 2010. He also concludes that three of the five perpetrators had some sort of mental or psychological disorders. This study also approaches the weapons

used by lone wolf terrorists in the attacks and notes that they vary as much as the terrorists themselves adding that the most used weapons used by these type of terrorists are firearms and bombs. This research also found out that 43% of the cases used firearms, 28% cases used explosives, armed hijacking of aircrafts and buses in 16% of the cases and 6% in arsons. According to Simon's et al (2013) research, the lone-wolf terrorism firearm use is highest in the United States. It notices an interesting trend in the type of weapons used by different types of terrorists stating that firearms are mostly used by lone wolf terrorists as fire bombing and bombs are mostly utilized by international terrorists. According to McCauley, Moskalenko and Van Son's (2013) study, the reason for using bombs is that bombs require training and ability technically lacked by most lone wolfs.

Finally, Simon's (2013) study published in 2014 focusing on lone wolf terrorist radicalization processes and motives showed that a number of lone wolf terrorists used the internet to radicalize themselves combined with personal grievances leading to terrorist extremist views. This study cannot be generalized due to the fact that it only focused on three successful terrorist attacks attributed to lone wolfs. Two of them concur with McCauley, Moskalenko and Van Son et al (2013) claim that psychological disturbance among individuals is the fuelling factor in this type of terrorism. All the three studies support Simon's (2013) claims that this terrorist type has varying methods of radicalization and its activities and attacks have been on the rise in the past decade.

4. Radicalization Process

Radicalization process that leads terrorists to action is a widely debated topic despite that fact that no standard profiler on how this radicalization exists but notes that it results from individual processes, socio-political and cultural situations and interpersonal relationship (Gill, Horgan, & Deckert, 2014). According to McCauley, Moskalenko and Van Son (2013), influencing factors to lone-wolf terrorists encompass personal aversions, negatively perceived career developments, depressions, extremist movement interactions, militant publications and literature, socio-political radicalization and polarization and admired terrorist activities carried out somewhere else.

The internet can radicalize persons even right under the watch of the law enforcement agencies due to its nature of being ambiguous and anonymous making it a perfect and undetectable vehicle and means of radicalization. On the premises of somebody's assessment on a study entitled 'Lone wolves typology: lone Islamist terrorists' primary analysis, the radicalization process is based on personal agendas which is not the case with international group-based terrorists. Gill, Dickert and Horgan (2014) in a report on violent nature of Islamist extremism concurred with this McCauley, Moskalenko and Van Son's (2013) assessment on radicalization process of lone wolves. In this report, four steps of radicalization process are detailed and the same primary principles apply in this topic.

Pre-Radicalization is radicalization process origin point before minds are made. This is the situation of the Lone wolves before they get exposed to Jihadi-Salafi ideologies and adopt them.

Self-Identification is stage of the radicalizations process in which external and internal factors affect individuals and start exploring extremist ideologies slowly drifting from original identity and start associating with people of the same ideologies and start adopting these ideologies as their own.

Indoctrination is the radicalization stage where potential lone wolves progress and intensify their beliefs and fully adopt jihadi-salafi ideologies and conclude that existing circumstances require support to further the cause.

Jihadization is the radicalization phase following indoctrination where individuals accept their personal responsibility to take part in terror activities and do self designation on personal levels as holly warriors (mujahedeen) and begins plans launching terror attacks including planning, preparation and execution bas furtherance acts.

Spaaij and Hamm's (2015) paths of radicalization is also confirmed by two-thirds of case studies looked into herein and are therefore important classification tools to both international group based terrorists and lone wolf terrorists. In an article entitled 'what is lone-wolf terrorism?' Gill, Horgan and Deckert, (2014) et al approach lone wolf terrorism personal agenda by theorizing that violence perpetrated by lone-wolf terrorists may be response to other extremist's increased isolation. The isolation occurs for a range of reasons including rejection by group and personal turmoil and the potential lone-wolf terrorist interacts with extremist group and as result has a way of relieving themselves of personal frustrations by way of extremist culture participation (Brynielsson, Horndahl, Johansson, Kaati, Mårtenson, & Svenson, 2013). Separation between the potential lone-

wolf terrorist and extremist group occurs at some point, and once the main group isolates a lone-wolf, he loses ability to conduct big scale terror and seeks way of releasing the mounting frustration.

Simon (2013) contends that the lone-wolf may take violence as extremist world restoration means. The basis of this theory is personal interaction and subsequent rejection by an established larger group encouraging the perpetrator to act and is therefore not party to any terrorist group and is propelled by the rejection to go on the loose and unleash terror.

5. Counterterrorism Policies

Many policies have been fronted to confront terrorism all over the world after September 11th attacks but only a few people specifically recognize and try to approach solution on lone-wolf terrorism as a concern to national security (Spaaij & Hamm, 2015). According to Brynielsson, Horndahl, Johansson, Kaati, Mårtenson, and Svenson, (2013), the most affected countries such as the United Kingdom, the European Union and the United States and others formulated policies and passed laws on prevention and arrest of terrorists.

The patriotic act of 2011 enacted in the United States aiming to unite and strengthen America by way of providing required tools in the interception and obstruction of terrorism in a big scale enhanced it's the nation's ability to confront and combat international terrorist groups but blatantly ignores domestic terrorists (Brynielsson, Horndahl, Johansson, Kaati, Mårtenson, & Svenson, 2013).

Terrorism prevention and intelligence reform act (2004) is one of the laws that deal with lone wolf terrorist stating that non-USA person engaging in terrorist activities is considered a foreign power agent under FISA helping in the preparation for international terrorism(Gill, Horgan & Deckert, 2014). The act does not change court order applications that authorize physical search and electronic surveillance under Foreign Intelligence Surveillance Act. This provision does not deal with domestic lone wolf terrorism but foreign national lone wolf terrorists.

Other western nations have also enacted policies to help combat and suppress terrorist activities. The United Kingdom had passed counterterrorism laws even before the 9/11 attacks including the terrorism act of 2000 that laid legal grounds for the prosecution of terrorists (Hamm & Spaaij, 2015). The United Kingdom in December 2011 enacted the terrorism investigation and prevention act which protects the country from unprosecutable and undeportable small number of foreign nationals who pose threat to national security (Berntzen & Sandberg, 2014).

Germany among many nations in Europe also that undertook measures to detect , prevent and deter terrorism among the European Union member states by having a policy in place to counter threats based on four key pillars as outlined in the European Union Counterterrorism Strategy that combats terror in general (Hamm & Spaaij, 2015). The European Union coordinates policies within member nations by using this counterterrorism strategy. The first of the four pillars deals with member states terrorism prevention and attempts to deal with terrorist radicalization and recruitment by

identification of methods, instruments and propaganda terrorists employ (Appleton, 2014).

Berntzen & Sandberg, 2014 argue that these terrorism deterrence policies rely on the key pillars for members of the Europeans Union namely development of common approaches to problem behavior spot on tackling, holding incitement and recruitment checks in marked environments, intercultural dialogue development, and explaining of European union policies to better, promote economic prosperity, good governance and education through assistive programs, continued research on terrorism and sharing of analyses and experiences.

These areas are important in detecting and combating lone-wolf terrorism as well as international terrorism (Berntzen & Sandberg, 2014). The second area deals with member states terrorism protection by reducing the vulnerability of targets and limiting of attack impacts. It aims to establish border security action collectively besides transport and other cross border infrastructures. Becker (2014) contends that the EU hardens its policy infrastructures and protects its member states by fortifying borders against general terrorist threats; this focus is though mostly on international terrorism.

Another point pursues terrorists within member states across borders with respect to human rights and international law. By this it aims to cut terrorist off access to materials such as arms and explosives, interfere with organization of terrorist networks and recruitment agencies and confront non-profit association misuse (Becker, 2014). The European Union has enacted policies to stop terrorism financing and disrupt terrorist

communication especially via the internet. The union takes a general perspective look at terror and does not specifically look at lone-wolf terrorist activities. Last of the pillars respond to terrorist attacks and this is outlined to match the response to natural, technological or manmade disasters. The union has all resources and assets that all member states have in case there is a terror attack. This pillar, from the policy concerns, is designed to respond to all terrorist activities including lone-wolf terrorism. Spaaij and Hamm (2015) in an article called 'next lone-wolf attack prevention capabilities' points out key policies that need amendment or creation to confront lone-wolf terrorism. This thesis examines case studies to determine the validity of policies with reference to somebody's policy suggestions.

6. The Seriousness of the Threat

Simon (2013) states that in 2014 ISIS had sent some of its fighters to conduct attacks in the US as retaliatory response to US air strikes in Iraq and stated that lone-wolf terrorists were on the spot despite the fact that they are difficult to detect and disrupt. In 2003 Al Qaeda and in 2014 ISIS called on sympathizers to get up to arms without instructions and this would only be possible through undetected lone-wolf terrorists to attack the West since these nations have developed and established systems to detect and prevent cross border terrorism.

Al Qaeda member named Abhu Jihad al-Misri authored an article entitled 'How to fight alone' and circulated it widely. The same calls were also made by a writer of Salafi named Abhu Musab al-Suri advocating for individual, small or autonomous cell

terrorist acts (Becker, 2014). In the calls, the laid bare global conflict strategy by resistance by individuals and cells keeping links to organizations limited to avoid detection. Nations have recognized and validated the threats posed by lone-wolf terrorists and passed legislations to detect and confront the growing threat. France, for instance, has created and adopted new terrorism legislations to adjust to the threats posed by lone-wolves to add to those posed by old trends of international terrorism in response to the calls by ISIS (Gill, Horgan & Deckert, (2014). French laws block entry to persons with relatives mentioned or have been involved in terrorist activities and punishes lone wolves established to be planning attacks on their own.

Chile also followed suit by passing anti-terrorism law that provided grounds for the charging of lone wolf offenders in response to the threats posed by lone wolf terrorists (Appleton, 2014). It is the seriousness of the threats posed by lone wolves that governments are passing and enacting laws to respond mutating terrorist activities.

The FBI acknowledges the threat posed by lone wolves and states in their 2005-2009 Strategic Plan that lone-wolves will be in years to come the most significant national security threat (Becker, 2014). Lone wolves use unnatural and unconventional methodology with limited resources to create high profile and utterly destructive attacks that can have significant damage effects on infrastructure and effect chaos. Of the 50 stopped known terror plots against the United States from 2007 compiled by Gill, Horgan and Deckert, (2014), forty two of them were lone-wolf activities. Lone-wolf terrorist

attack numbers have increased and their activities intensified and this is enough proof that the threats are real and on the rise.

The life cycle of lone wolves in relation to terrorist who are group based is a bit longer and because of that they even pose more threats. Feldman's (2013) study brief contends that lone wolves have longer life spans than widely known terrorists. They estimate that participants of group terrorists hardly survive 380 days after committing attacks while lone-wolves survive even much longer than this estimated at averagely 1,900 days from preparation date to arrest date unless caught and neutralized in the act. Simon (2013) confirms that the longer a terrorist lives freely and avoid arrest the longer he continues to wreak havoc. McCauley, Moskalenko and Van Son et al (2013) argues that lone wolves do not live for longer than common terrorists as most of them are caught and killed in the act due to poor strategies and planning before the launch of attacks. Spaaij and Hamm (2015) state that the fact that lone wolves live for longer makes it urgent to detect, investigate and apprehend them since being left freely may be at the expense of innocent lives.

The life-cycle of loan wolf terrorists

McCauley (2013) found out that 51 out of the 62 US homeland terrorist attacks or plots are homegrown without formal connection to and has called for increased security at federal buildings and cities and has warned security apparatus in the United States to prepare for more attacks. This number equates to 82% of recent attacks being home grown lone wolf terrorist attacks and is the main reason to take the threats more seriously

(Cohen, Johansson, Kaati, & Mork, 2014). Due to these numbers and the length of lone-wolf life cycle, the lone wolf terrorist attacks are considered mainstream terrorism form.

CHAPTER 3: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework used in this thesis is that one McCauley and Moskalenko (2014) sought to create. Lone wolf terrorist profiles and identify their movements from radical opinions to action. This theoretical framework was selected from a literature review on radicalization models and frameworks which did not wholly focus on lone wolf terrorism. A compilation of books, reports, journals, articles, hearings and reports by Spaaij and Hamm (2015) concur with McCauley and Moskalenko (2014) framework offer the most up-to-date recent perspectives with regards to the thesis research questions. Two pyramids were come up with, first on radical opinions and the second on radical actions. It was concluded that lone wolf terrorist' most dangerous indicator is the combination of radical opinions and means and opportunity to launch actions.

Hypotheses and Problems

A large number of scholars contend that lone-wolf terrorist profiles do not exist and so common characteristics can be discerned such as background of one-wolf terrorist, attack planning and attack aspects as they can be used as counterterrorism and law enforcement potential lone-wolf terrorist tip-off basis. This thesis contends that features can be used to inform policy changes after creating lone-wolf terrorist preliminary profile creation based on common themes. Quite a number of policies have been formulated and adopted and has help confront international group terrorism, that for they to work in the

context of lone-wolf terror they must be changed to fit in current trends and emerging issues in terrorism such as lone-wolf terrorism.

Terrorism Detection and Prevention Methods

This chapter delves into the need to adapt policies to enable detection and deterrence of lone wolf terrorists by looking at the policy issues witnessed in the case studies. The policy issues can be addressed by adaptation of policies to detect and detect lone-wolf terrorists.

Countries have a number of policies and laws that enable them confront domestic and international terror as depicted in the first chapter of this thesis. The FBI of the United States as a governmental agency plays a crucial role in detecting and responding to internal terrorist threats. The FBI as depicted in the case studies have shown lack of proper methods of detecting and deterring lone wolf terrorist threats and this is brought about by weak policy guidelines that need to be changed to enable it prevent domestic lone wolf terrorist acts. This policy weakness is attributed to underlying struggle between civil liberty protection and lone wolf terrorism prevention that need adjustment and balance to cater for all needs without infringing on the rights of the civilians. The case studies point to the need for policy improvements and creation in the quest to combat terrorist threats by reviewing the miscues.

1. Inter-Law Enforcement Agency Information Sharing

This is one of the proposals by Spaaij and Hamm (2015) to help curb lone wolf terrorism in the policy changes. Law enforcement agencies do not share information among themselves just like in the case of the FBI in the first two case studies. This is not a new item for action in the quest to combat terrorism domestically. This issue was raised of the FBI after the 9/11 attack. The FBI did not share information on possible and imminent terrorist attack and terrorist activity investigations with local and state law enforcement agencies as is the first two case studies of this thesis. The FBI has since failed to stop lone wolf terrorist activities that have claimed a lot of innocent lives. Fort Hood shootings and the Boston Bombings would have been avoided if information was shared. In the Boston bombing case study, Tamerlan's link to terrorism would have been established if the information shared by the Russian law enforcement agency was taken seriously by the FBI and shared with state and local law enforcement agencies and would have led to his arrest after he assaulted a former girlfriend. The local police would have taken steps to interview the girlfriend which would have prompted her to share information on his involvement with jihadists. The bombings would have been detected in time and stopped if information sharing was prioritized since the elder of the brothers was the leader. The local police have knowledge on localities better than federal agency and therefore have a better possibility of handling impending attacks like in this case.

2. Use of Local Cyber Assets to Assess Terrorism Nexus

There is need for cyber investigation capabilities in large towns like Boston and Oslo and should be made a basic focus since most terrorism plans and communications

together with radicalization occurs through the internet. Law enforcement agencies can inspect the contents viewed by potential lone wolf terrorists, a move that would have helped prevent the Boston marathon bombings. Chances are that the FBI either ignored or did not look at the internet activities during the assessment of Major Nidal and Tamerlan for possible terror attacks in the first two case scenarios. This move can not only apply in the case of lone wolf terrorism investigation and prevention but also in international terrorism as well. There were reasonable grounds on internet activities of both Hasan and Tamerlan's cases prior to their acts of terrorism on the possibility of attacks.

3. Use of Community Outreach Programs and Tools

This also appeared to be a major weakness in the first two case studies of this thesis as they are key in ensuring trust in local communities and would help greatly in thwarting terror attacks if effective community outreach programs are put in place. If the community was engaged in the Boston bombings and Fort Hood shootings, terror suspects would have been detected in time as the community would help in the assessment process by providing crucial information that would have boosted efforts of the investigative body. On a daily basis, community members interacted with these would-be terrorists that would harm them. They at some point noticed behavior changes among these would-be lone-wolf terrorists that cannot be noticed by short term assessment. The communities can offer a broader view of the imminent attacks as would have happened in all the three case studies in this thesis. Law enforcement agencies should embrace community outreach programs to establish links with terrorism among suspects.

It is simple to establish terrorist connection among suspects since most of them preach violent ideologies in the case of Islamic views as they radicalize. Community outreach programs would have helped establish links with terrorism by providing information such as these preachings. Neighborhood watch programs are important as they have been successful in other parts of the world to watch and provide information on criminal gangs without violation of civil liberties of the citizens.

4. Joint Investigation by Law Enforcement Agencies

The lead function of certain law enforcement agencies charged with the responsibility of shielding the public from internal terrorist attacks should be devolved to even lower and smaller law enforcement agency formations like the local police and others so that terror and peculiar behaviors are detected in time due to the fact that intelligence on terror activities are collected from various fronts thereby building a stronger case when the information and evidence are shared between them. The Boston marathon was first considered a criminal act and it was the responsibility of the local police to protect the public from criminal acts. If the FBI and the local police acted in concert in the case of Boston Marathon, more information would have been acquired as the two bodies investigated the matter. Policies that frustrate information flow between laws enforcement agencies should therefore be changed or improved to enable effective and conclusive investigation carrying out. Like in the first two case studies of this thesis, law enforcement agencies may fail to follow up on crucial leads that would lead to apprehension and restraining of suspects to avoid possible attacks when they are left to

roam freely on the basis of lack of enough evidence that would have instead been acquired by multiple agencies working together and sharing intelligence. The FBI attributed its failure to detect and contain terror attacks in these case studies to lack of information sharing and disconcerted efforts in the fight against homegrown terror.

Failure to change and adopt policies that would help connect dots in efforts to identify terror threats and suspects would result in lone-wolf terrorist attacks success as in the first two case studies.

5. Conclusive and Comprehensive Assessment of Terror Suspects

Most lone-wolf terror suspects at certain points in their lives before the attack attract the attention of law enforcement agencies. Cross border countries such as the United Kingdom should share terrorist policies and regulations that even when suspects cross borders they still remain under watch of the security agencies. Information should be shared for a comprehensive and conclusive terrorist suspect assessment. If this was applied in the case of Anders Breivick, the Norwegian authorities would have contained the two lone wolf attacks launched by him. Breivick landed himself in the watch list of Norwegian authorities when he bought large amounts of fertilizers which he would later use to make bombs that would go off outside government buildings in Oslo. A conclusive and comprehensive assessment would have found out that the fertilizers were not meant for his rented firm but for terroristic plans that could have been foiled by authorities, or if not the case, an interview with him by the authorities would have made him change or abandon his plans knowing very well that he is in the police watch list. Policies need to

be in place to ensure that suspects in watch lists are conclusively assessed to determine links with terrorist groups.

This conclusive assessment can only be achieved through common information sharing that relates suspects to possible terrorist activities. It is imperative that European nations and any other nation susceptible to terrorist attacks adapt FBI's information sharing between state and local security formations on terror related activities. The case of Europe is unique in that one can cross borders to neighboring countries with little scrutiny as with Breivick's case in which he bought the large amounts of fertilizers in a cross border country and transported to Norway without enough scrutiny. Europe should adopt systems that track, monitor and share information with among member states. Europe should share information with even non-member states so that it responds to terror threats in time before they wreak havoc on infrastructure and lives.

6. Increasing Police Geo-Locations and Intensifying Patrols

Norwegian police authorities are restricted from carrying firearms with dotted geo-location of police stations. Increased police officer and station number serves to increase the level of vigilance in the force due to increased patrols that might come across suspicious activities and intervene before the acts are committed. This situation gave him the way of setting off bombs in Oslo and conducting active shooting in Utoya.

A change of policy should be approached in Norway to allow law enforcement officers to carry firearms and not be constrained when a terrorist strikes due to incapacitation. The Norwegian police have the least number of times in the world that

they have opened fire on aggressors. Breivick took to consideration the ill-equipment of the police in terms of little assistance due to the fact that they don't carry guns around and distanced locations of police stations and restrictions on the use of guns. He took advantage of this and inflicted maximum casualties since he had enough time. The European nations should learn from the Breivick case study in terms of the use of guns and location of police stations together with patrols. This would ensure high vigilance levels and capacity in terms of protecting citizens.

High number of police officers and station would also ensure that the police can sufficiently monitor and track terrorism nexus by examining internet activities that would tip off the police on planned activities and radicalization materials. Breivick's case was also facilitated by the internet since he used this network to radicalize himself by gaining ideological and operational mindsets and strategies through the posts on the right-wing and anti-Islamic forums. Simon (2013) notes that Breivick was very innovative and secretive in the way he used the internet that did not arouse any suspicion. He used the internet to inquire information on how to travel to Prague from Oslo by road to go and buy weapons and chemicals. He flected his action over the internet by setting up companies that are e-commerce-based as he sought to buy weapons and chemicals that he would use to make the bomb.

The internet is a vital information gathering tool and can be used to track potential lone wolf terrorists and Norway should therefore increase the number of police officers and police stations with the capacity to keep eyes on internet activities.

CHAPTER SUMMARY

Countries need policy adoption and adaptation to be in a position to deal with lone-wolf terrorists. Many policies are already in place to curb international group-based terrorism; they have to be changed to deal with this emerging trend in terrorist activities and nations are inadequately prepared for it. The three case studies in this thesis show clear cases of failed detection and intervention procedures due to old policies that do not cater for lone-wolf terrorists. Governments need to learn from their past mistakes and put public safety first to avoid the rising number of cases attributed to lone wolf terrorism.

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH DESIGN

A case on lone-wolf terrorism was required to meet the definition in this thesis. Ninety-eight cases were discovered cutting across 1940 to 2013. This sample represented all lone wolf scenarios and cases. Information was therefore extracted from the 98 cases' research, memoirs, government reports, journalistic sources, biographies, documentaries, encyclopedia and court documents. The information gathered cuts across the ninety-eight cases through different variables. Thirty eight of the cases took place in the pre-9/11 attacks while the rest took place after it. Fifteen of the post 9/11 lone wolf cases were committed by law enforcement sting operations. This thesis identifies current trends and emerging issues in lone wolf terrorism by comparing pre and post 9/11 cases in full spectrum.

Methods of Data Collection

The findings and recommendations in this thesis were developed from substantial research into lone-wolf terrorism open source literature in existence. Interviews on experts, attorneys, policy makers and academics on the subject supplemented the research. Two data sets by Hamm (2015) and Spaaij (2012) were relied on to analyze the problem scope and trends in terrorism. Both dataset authors agree that an individual has to commit violence or threaten to be called lone-wolf terrorist. This means that the datasets agree with lone-wolf definitions in this thesis. Academic literature sources have described cybercrime as one of lone-wolf terrorist attacks but this thesis will not concentrate on computer network as terrorist attack methodology. The most known

methodology by lone wolf terrorists is violence on human lives and property and not cyber attacks. The definition does not though rule out the possibility of using cyber attacks to interfere with national security.

Sources and Methods

This paper comparatively looks at methods in a structured and focused perspective in three lone-wolf case studies. Each case is structured to standardize each terrorist analysis and information logical sequencing. Since lone wolf terrorism is a global problem with no boundaries, the analysis of each case study is aimed at examining the background of the perpetrators and determines if the case is lone terrorism, then the lone terrorism specifics and reviews of findings of documents and summery of key points. The laws, policies and approaches in counterterrorism are assessed in they were capable of detecting and preventing lone terrorism in addition to the new approaches and adaptations.

Research Limitations

Case studies was the method for this thesis but had disadvantages that have to be acknowledged to evade pitfalls. Case studies do not have rigor since investigators do not follow systematic procedure and allow bias in their findings and conclusions. This thesis strictly followed systematic procedures for the sake of valid and reliable case studies. This thesis relied heavily on secondary sources but still provides insights into issues around lone-wolf terrorism and radicalization. The triangulated data and information was retrieved from reliable sources. This method was chosen over primary sources such as

observations and interviews despite the fact that they provide extensive insights into topic under research. This is due to the fact that there have not been interviews with lone wolves. Primary data collection would bring on board a large range of information and methods but due to the fact that most of them end up dead in the act, there cannot be interviews. Those who survive and prosecuted end-up in maximum security prisons that hardly allow interactions with the perpetrator. Due to this difficulty in obtaining primary data, this thesis relied on case analyses. Depending on case analyses left important factors out such as intentions and motivation of the terrorists to support hypotheses and propositions. Case study findings are not also generalizable due to lack of research. This research did not put into considerations ethical concerns as it could not limit this study. Information and identities that required ethical approval were not accessible so the thesis relied on information available to the public. Further research on primary sources will raise ethical that would require ethical considerations. Researchers attempting to access these groups will require research question and interview guidance so that they don't culturally or religiously offend respondents. Researchers will have to use translators or religious community members in limiting ethical concerns. There will still be limitations of methods in examining lone wolf terrorism cases until generalized research is conducted.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION

Lone wolf terrorism

This form of terrorism poses quite unpredictable and puzzling security threat of terrorism. The first chapter of this thesis looks into the issues of lone wolf terrorism by first defining individual terrorism acts not controlled nor influenced by outside orders from international terrorist organizations. The chapter explains that those lone wolf terrorists may have had links in the past with international terrorist groups that supply them with ideological and motivational provisions. Another issue highlighted is the identification of lone wolf terrorists and admits that this is difficult in that they are part of the society and might plan their action peacefully undetected and can strike at any time anywhere.

Chapter two examines Nidal Hasan's Fort Hood shooting spree case study. The chapter explains why the act was lone wolf terror incident. It also provides information on the use of the internet by lone wolf terrorists in radicalization and planning and law enforcement agencies have failed in lone-wolf terrorism detection. The chapter approaches the effectiveness of community outreach programs in intervening factors in information seeking efforts as would have happened in the first two case studies where Washington DC mosque community leaders would have done by providing details thereby helping protect the public against such attacks.

The third chapter handles details around the Boston marathon bombings as an act of terrorism act by lone-wolfs since they used the internet as a characteristic around lone

wolf terrorist planning and execution. Here too the community's role is recognized as having the ability to help contain terror threats by providing crucial information to law enforcement authorities that link the suspect with terror. If this avenue is properly utilized, law enforcement agencies will be in a better shape to detect and stop pending terror acts.

The fourth chapter analyses Anders Breivick's attack on Norway and declared it a case of lone wolf terrorism. It explains how he used the internet to access radicalization and planning information and buying materials that he would use to make bombs for his attack outside government buildings. The chapter also talks about how his parents and other community members noticed changes in his behaviors that provided information that if were to be used would have helped contain acts of the suspect. This reaffirms the community's role in the fight against lone wolf terrorism.

Chapter five focuses on possible solutions to detecting and containing terrorism and proposes major policy adjustment and adoptions to enable nations deal with lone wolf terrorism. The case studies herein provide grounds for policy changes in efforts to detect and stop terrorist plans. The use of internet is persistent in all case studies and this thesis recommends measures to have an eye over the internet to keep terrorist activities in check so that plans can be detected in due time for action. The thesis proposes in this chapter that the government should also use the internet to curb terrorist plans just like lone wolf terrorist use it to acquire harmful information that end up radicalizing them further. The bottom line in this chapter is that identification and detection of terrorists is

important so that monitoring is made easier. The chapter confirms the initial hypothesis that lone wolf terrorism can be stopped. World governments must therefore keep themselves posted with trends that merge in terrorism do that policies are adjusted and created in time for detection and deterrence of terrorist activities.

Areas for further research

The growth and success of lone wolf terror plots will lay the basis for further research. But as things stand right now, areas for further research is the use of the internet in the perpetration of terrorist activities and consequent use of the internet by security organs. Another area for future research is the need to reexamine such countries as Australia and Israel's lone wolf terrorist cases and counterterrorism policies since they have larger populations of second generation Muslims population since two-thirds of the case studies in this thesis point to them as main potential perpetrators. Another area for further research is the factors that lead to radicalization of would-be lone wolf terrorists that are not Muslims. These areas for future research are very important if lone wolf terrorist would be detected in time and deterred.

Conclusion

Law enforcement and intelligence agencies have in the last decade been responding to terrorist incident rise and are increasingly becoming adept when it comes to detection and disruption of terror plots that are mutating to small scale simpler assaults. Terrorist groups in response to this are inspiring their sympathizers to take over small scale attacks. They have established that lone-wolf actors have huge success

chances even without help or connection to a group. Lone-wolf terrorists present detection and disruption challenges to law enforcement and intelligence agencies as they have no connection with terrorist groups and therefore do not take commands from them.

The analysis from database construction from across the globe suggest that improving the understanding of lone wolf actors in terms of their behavior and activities will help countering lone wolf terrorism and will help governments and workers take security measures.

Group-based international terrorism claim a large percentage of attention given to terrorism since 9/11 attacks leaving lone-wolf terrorism not well researched and unprepared for as seen in the case studies in this thesis (Teich, 2013). This case shows that there exist diverse types of lone-wolf terrorists meaning that they can be anyone in the society. The case studies under examination in this thesis prove that lone wolf terrorism, just like international one, is detectable and preventable. Detecting this type of terrorism is challenging and this thesis proposes policy changes in this struggle.

References

- Appleton, C. (2014). Lone wolf terrorism in Norway. *The International Journal of Human Rights*, 18(2), 127-142.
- Becker, M. (2014). Explaining lone wolf target selection in the United States. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 37(11), 959-978.
- Berntzen, L. E., & Sandberg, S. (2014). The collective nature of lone wolf terrorism: Anders Behring Breivik and the anti-Islamic social movement. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 26(5), 759-779.
- Brynielsson, J., Horndahl, A., Johansson, F., Kaati, L., Mårtenson, C., & Svenson, P. (2013). Harvesting and analysis of weak signals for detecting lone wolf terrorists. *Security Informatics*, 2(1), 11.
- Cohen, K., Johansson, F., Kaati, L., & Mork, J. C. (2014). Detecting linguistic markers for radical violence in social media. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 26(1), 246-256.
- Feldman, M. (2013). Comparative lone wolf terrorism: Toward a heuristic definition. *Democracy and security*, 9(3), 270-286.
- Gill, P., Horgan, J., & Deckert, P. (2014). Bombing alone: Tracing the motivations and antecedent behaviors of lone-actor terrorists. *Journal of forensic sciences*, 59(2), 425-435.

- Gruenewald, J., Chermak, S., & Freilich, J. D. (2013). Far-right lone wolf homicides in the United States. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism, 36*(12), 1005-1024.
- Hamm, M. S., & Spaaij, R. F. (2015). *Lone wolf terrorism in America: Using knowledge of radicalization pathways to forge prevention strategies*.
- Kaplan, J., Lööw, H., & Malkki, L. (2014). Introduction to the Special Issue on Lone Wolf and Autonomous Cell Terrorism. *Terrorism and Political Violence, 26*(1), 1-12.
- McCauley, C., & Moskalenko, S. (2014). Toward a profile of lone wolf terrorists: What moves an individual from radical opinion to radical action. *Terrorism and Political Violence, 26*(1), 69-85.
- McCauley, C., Moskalenko, S., & Van Son, B. (2013). Characteristics of lone-wolf violent offenders: A comparison of assassins and school attackers. *Perspectives on Terrorism, 7*(1).
- Michael, G. (2014). Counterinsurgency and Lone Wolf Terrorism. *Terrorism and Political Violence, 26*(1), 45-57.
- Phillips, P. J. (2013). *In pursuit of the lone wolf terrorist: investigative economics and new horizons for the economic analysis of terrorism*. Nova Science Publishers, Inc..

- Reid Meloy, J., & Yakeley, J. (2014). The violent true believer as a “lone wolf”—psychoanalytic perspectives on terrorism. *Behavioral sciences & the law*, 32(3), 347-365.
- Simon, J. D. (2013). Lone wolf terrorism. *Amherst, NY: Prometheus Books*.
- Simon, J. D. (2016). *Lone wolf terrorism: Understanding the growing threat*. Prometheus Books.
- Spaaij, R., & Hamm, M. S. (2015). Key issues and research agendas in lone wolf terrorism. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 38(3), 167-178.
- Striegler, J. L. (2013). Early detection of the lone wolf: advancement of counter-terrorism investigations with an absence or abundance of information and intelligence. *Journal of Policing, Intelligence and Counter Terrorism*, 8(1), 35-53.
- Teich, S. (2013). Trends and developments in lone wolf terrorism in the western world: An analysis of terrorist attacks and attempted attacks by Islamic extremists. *International Institute for Counter-Terrorism*. October.